

How systematic are systematic literature searches?

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Abstract

Systematic literature reviews and meta-analyses have gained importance due to the increasing rates of academic publications and the need to evaluate and integrate findings. The systematic literature search using databases and platforms is the essential first step in the process of conducting research syntheses. We investigated the replicability of literature searches conducted within two databases (ERIC, PsycINFO) and two search platforms (ProQuest, Web of Science). Fifteen researchers from different institutions performed identical searches guided by a manual. We found that ERIC searches were replicable, but the type of quotation marks used in the search string mattered. Despite PsycINFO being frequently reported in published reviews and meta-analyses, none of the researchers had direct access, but used alternative platforms (EBSCOhost or Ovid) to access PsycINFO. Using a specific platform (either EBSCOhost, Ovid, or ProQuest) to indirectly search the databases, PsycINFO and/or ERIC provided identical search results across institutions. However, the indirect search via platforms mostly delivered different numbers of hits compared to the direct search in the databases. Additionally, the searches via platforms identified publications that partially differed from those found by direct searches in the databases. Web of Science searches showed a low degree of replicability; results differed between institutions with regard to the number of hits and in the composition of the identified publications. To increase replicability, we suggest expanding reporting guidelines like PRISMA-S to require researchers to publish their full initial search hits.

Keywords

Systematic literature search, Replicability, Reporting guidelines, Literature database, Search platform, PRISMA-S.

Introduction

The rate of academic publications grows exponentially (Bornmann & Mutz, 2015) and challenges researchers to remain up to date (Landhuis, 2016). Given this challenge and the need to integrate findings, it is not surprising that publishing of systematic reviews and meta-analyses increases, too. Newman and Gough (2020, p.4) describe that “reviews can be used for making claims about what we know and do not know about a phenomenon and also about what new research we need to undertake to address questions that are unanswered.” That is, systematic reviews and meta-analyses aim to systematically organize, evaluate, and summarize research, synthesizing existing evidence for a research field by identifying relations, inconsistencies, and research gaps. Journals on subject-specific education or education in general which focus on publishing systematic syntheses are highly ranked and prestigious (e.g., *Studies in Science Education* or *Review of Educational Research*, respectively). Moreover, applied sciences typically need to build on reliable findings from more basic research when doing research in the field (e.g., subject-specific education supervenes on basic psychological processes). Providing this reliable basis requires systematic reviews and meta-analyses, like other methodologies of science, to be replicable and transparent (Cram et al., 2020). When trying to replicate the literature search in a recent publication about biology education, we ran into difficulties. Despite being provided with extensive additional information about how to specify the literature search by the authors, we did not obtain the same number of search hits. To investigate this problem, we conducted a small exploratory study. The study reveals issues with the replicability of systematic literature

searches which constitute the starting point of all systematic reviews and meta-analyses.

To assure the quality, transparency, and replicability of systematic reviews and meta-analyses, the research community has devised guidelines specifying how to report the identification, selection, and appraisal of studies. The common guideline is PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses; Page et al., 2021) which has recently been updated to PRISMA-S (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses literature - Search extension; PRISMA-S Group et al., 2021). The PRISMA-S guideline emphasizes the central importance of the initial literature search. Therefore, PRISMA-S expanded, compared to PRISMA, the guidance on reporting the literature search. For example, authors should now disclose the search strategies for all used databases, not just one. In general, reporting guidelines are essential to structure and support the complex methodology of systematic reviews and meta-analyses.

The updated PRISMA-S guideline reflects an important development. Technological progress in developing and constantly improving literature databases and search platforms has greatly facilitated access to scientific publications (Patra, 2017). Databases are defined by the National Research Council (1999, p. 15) as a "collection of related data and information [...] organized to permit search and retrieval or processing and reorganizing." Search platforms provide access to several databases simultaneously. They have become the primary source of literature searches since nowadays systematic literature searches usually involve searching multiple databases (Lam & McDiarmid, 2017); for example, searching the databases ERIC and PsycINFO simultaneously via the platform ProQuest. While differences between databases and their suitability for specific research fields have been described in detail (e.g., Jacso, 2005), research on the stability and accuracy of databases and search platforms is still limited (e.g., Pozsgai et al., 2021). Furthermore, PRISMA-S does not require researchers to fully report the raw data, that is, the complete list of initial search hits. Given that the state of research identified through searches in databases and platforms determines the conclusions, suggestions, and recommendations derived from systematic reviews and meta-analyses, it is necessary to investigate the replicability, or put differently, to investigate how systematic these literature searches are.

The present study

The first step of a systematic review or meta-analysis is conducting literature searches. We investigated this first step. We focussed our investigation on databases and search platforms which are widely used in subject-specific education and educational and psychological sciences (i.e., ERIC, PsycINFO, ProQuest, Web of Science). These search engines are routinely employed for research syntheses in high-ranked journals such as *Studies in Science Education*, *Review of Educational Research*, or *Psychological Bulletin*. We chose a broad topic from biology education for the searches, wrote a step-by-step search manual, and asked researchers world-wide to run the searches. With this methodology, we tried to answer our general research question: Are the results of systematic literature searches in specific databases and search platforms replicable? We also intended to provide insights on whether searches via platforms (comprising several databases) deliver the same search hits as literature searches conducted directly in the individual databases.

Participants

We emailed 19 researchers (see Table 1) world-wide and asked them to run specific literature searches as described in a search manual. Importantly, it is a convenient sample. We contacted researchers who we know, the sample is neither representative nor random. All of these researchers are employed as post-docs or professors and conduct research within the domains of subject-specific education, educational or psychological sciences. Fifteen researchers answered and performed the searches as extensively as it was possible at their respective institutions (depending on their access to databases and platforms, see below for details). Moreover, the authors of the present study also conducted all searches logging into the databases and platforms from two different universities in Switzerland.

Method

We aimed to investigate the replicability of searches within four databases/platforms by comparing search outcomes across different locations worldwide. We chose the databases Education Resources Information Centre (ERIC) and PsycINFO and the two search platforms ProQuest (searching the databases ERIC and PsycINFO) and Web of Science (using the search in “all databases” option).

We wrote a step-by-step search manual for a biology education topic (the manual is available from the authors of the present study upon request). The search string was: evolution AND education AND “primary school”. In the manual, we specified how to export the search results and how to upload them to a secured cloud server. We sent the manual to researchers and asked them to conduct the searches within a specific week, so that it would be unlikely that search results were affected by updates. We urged the researchers to run the searches from within their university network or to log into this network (e.g., via VPN).

Results

We examined the replicability of search results by comparing the number of search hits across researchers. Furthermore, we determined whether the searches identified identical publications. We describe the findings for each database and platform in the following paragraphs (see Table 1 for an overview).

In ERIC, all searches delivered either 105 or 290 identical hits except for the Université de Bourgogne (France) with 92 hits and KU Leuven (Belgium), which after removing duplicates identified nine fewer publications, so 281. The difference between 105 and 290 search hits can be explained by the type of quotation marks used. When using straight quotation marks, single words are merged into a single search term (e.g., entering “primary school” will only identify publications that use the two words in this exact phrase). Curved quotation marks (“primary school”) do not create a phrase search. Given that we provided the search string with curved quotes (as we did not know about this subtle, but important difference before), copying and pasting resulted in more search hits (i.e., 290) compared to typing the search string directly into the database using straight quotation marks. Taken together, ERIC searches are rather consistent (with the exception of Université de Bourgogne, France, and KU Leuven, Belgium, which we cannot explain). However, importantly, the shape of the quotation marks matters.

PsycINFO is frequently reported as a tool for systematic searches in systematic reviews and meta-analyses. However, of all participating institutions, only the two institutions based in Switzerland had direct access (both obtained 42 hits). Some of the participants could however access PsycINFO via the search platforms Ovid or EBSCOhost. We included these searches in our analysis. Five participants accessed PsycINFO via Ovid; three obtained 34, the other two obtained 1943 hits. The reason for this large difference is unclear. A possible influence could be the use of quotation marks. However, to determine the exact cause, a more detailed systematic investigation is required. Two participants accessed PsycINFO via EBSCOhost, both obtained 37 identical hits. In addition, searching PsycINFO via EBSCOhost or Ovid resulted in the identification of five publications in each case (but not the same five) which were not found by searching PsycINFO directly. Taken together, there are strong variations depending on how PsycINFO is accessed.

Table 1. Number of initial search hits (including duplications) per institution/country for each database/ search platform

Country	City	Institution	ERIC	Database/Search platform		
				PsycINFO	ProQuest	Web of Science
Argentina	Neuquén	National University of Comahue	105	X	X	X
Australia	Sydney	University of Sydney	290	34 (via Ovid)	72 (only ERIC)	114
Austria	Graz	University of Graz	290	X	X	106
Belgium	Leuven	KU Leuven	290	X	X	10
Finland	Helsinki	University of Helsinki	105	34 (via Ovid)	72 (only ERIC)	140
France	Dijon	Université de Bourgogne	91	1943 (via Ovid)	X	131
Germany	Cologne	University of Cologne	290	X	72 (only ERIC)	50
Germany	Kiel	Leibniz Institute for Science and Mathematics Education	290	X	X	64
Germany	Leipzig	Leipzig University	290	X	X	95
Israel	Haifa	Technion - Israel Institute of Technology	290	X	72 (only ERIC)	X
Japan	Tokyo	Keio University	No response			
Luxembourg	Luxemburg-City	University of Luxembourg	No response			
Norway	Oslo	University of Oslo	105	34 (via Ovid)	X	140
Philippines	Los Baños	International Rice Research Institute	No response			
Sweden	Upsala	Uppsala University	290	37 (via EBSCO-host)	72 (only ERIC)	138
Switzerland	Zurich	ETH Zurich	290 59 (via Ovid) 73 (via EBSCO-host)	42	114 (PsycInfo: 42; ERIC: 72)	95

Switzerland	Goldau	University of Teacher Education Schwyz	290	42	114 (PsycInfo: 42; ERIC: 72)	74
UK	London	Birkbeck College	290	37 (via EBSCO-host)	X	141
UK	Oxford	Oxford University	290	1943 (via Ovid)	X	142
USA	Pittsburgh	Carnegie Mellon University	No response			
USA	Madison	University of Wisconsin-Madison	105	X	X	159

Note: X denotes that a search was not possible because researchers had no access to the database or platform from their institution. No response denotes that we received no answer to our request.

Using the search platform ProQuest to simultaneously run searches in PsycINFO and ERIC was also more problematic than we expected. Only the two institutions based in Switzerland had access to PsycINFO via ProQuest. This search delivered 42 search hits, which equals the number of hits if the search was conducted directly in PsycINFO. But, the 42 hits were not identical, six hits did not overlap. Access to ERIC via ProQuest was only available for seven researchers (incl. Switzerland) but delivered consistently 72 identical search hits. However, this number of hits is much lower compared to conducting the search directly in ERIC. In addition, the 72 hits do not represent a complete subsample of the hits from the direct search within ERIC; there are seven publications that are not identical. Using ERIC via EBSCOhost and Ovid, resulted in 73 and 59 hits, respectively. Again, these numbers are different compared to the direct search.

Web of Science showed a high degree of variation in the number of hits. The most hits were obtained at the University of Wisconsin-Madison (USA) with 156, the fewest at KU Leuven (Belgium) with 10 hits. Only the searches at University of Helsinki (Finland) and University of Oslo (Norway) resulted in the same number. In addition to these differences between countries, the institutional access also influenced the number of hits. That is, in Switzerland, there was a difference of 21 hits depending on the institution from which we accessed Web of Science. To determine the consistency of search hits for Web of Science, we first removed duplicates from all search results. Afterwards, we compared institutions to the institution with the highest number of hits (University of Wisconsin-Madison, USA). This analysis allowed investigating whether the hits were the same. Université de Bourgogne (France), University of Cologne (Germany), Leipzig University (Germany), University of Oslo (Norway), Uppsala University (Sweden), ETH Zurich (Switzerland), Birkbeck College (UK) differed from the identified studies at the University of Wisconsin-Madison (USA) by one and the same study. The reason for this discrepancy remains unclear. We checked whether it was caused by updates, but that was not the case. The strongest discrepancy was found between the University of Wisconsin-Madison (USA) and University of Graz (Austria). Nine hits obtained in Austria were not included in hits obtained at the University of Wisconsin-Madison (USA). Thus, the search platform Web of Science shows not only large differences in the total number of search hits but also inconsistencies with regard to which hits are obtained.

Discussion

The replicability of systematic reviews and meta-analyses depends on the initial literature search. With our exploratory study, we tested whether researchers world-wide would find the same search hits when using a search string for a topic from biology education in ERIC, PsycIN-

FO, ProQuest, and Web of Science. Considering all findings in a nutshell, systematic literature searches are not as systematic as most might expect.

We found that ERIC performs quite consistent across countries/institutions regarding the number of hits. However, when using quotation marks, care must be taken as the database only considers straight quotation marks as phrase markers. The susceptibility to errors due to this formal aspect may be high given that the ERIC "search tips" do not explicate the demand to use straight quotation marks.

The use of PsycINFO is often reported in systematic review and meta-analyses in the domains of science education, educational and psychological sciences. Surprisingly, none of the participants we asked to conduct the literature searches had direct access. Thus, we could not thoroughly evaluate the replicability of PsycINFO searches if it is accessed directly.

Several participants however accessed PsycINFO and/or ERIC indirectly via search platforms like ProQuest (as we requested in our manual), EBSCOhost or Ovid (we would like to thank all participants for this extra effort). Using ERIC via ProQuest yielded the same search results across countries/institutions. However, the number of studies identified via this indirect search of ERIC differed from the direct search within ERIC. This deviation between indirect and direct searches of ERIC was also detected when we accessed the platforms EBSCOhost and Ovid from ETH Zurich (Switzerland). Similar deviations between direct and indirect searches also emerged for PsycINFO when accessed via Ovid or EBSCOhost. That is, the search results were replicable if researchers used the same platform, but the platforms delivered different numbers of hits compared to the direct search. Only the PsycINFO search via ProQuest led to the same number of hits as the direct search in the database. It is, however, important to recap that among the participating institutions, only those based in Switzerland could access PsycINFO directly and via ProQuest. Moreover, conducting searches via platforms mostly resulted in the identification of a slightly different set of publication, i.e., publications that were not identified in the direct search. These findings clearly illustrate that platforms influence search results.

Finally, Web of Science showed strong variation in search results. The replicability regarding the number of hits across countries/institutions was low. In addition, the searches were not completely consistent. That is, the largest number of hits (obtained in the USA) did not comprise all studies found in other institutions. These findings resemble results of prior studies, which indicated similar problems with Web of Science (Gusenbauer & Haddaway, 2020; Pozsgai et al., 2021). The results provide only a first indication of basic problems with systematic literature searches. The study was exploratory; we did not precisely know what to expect. We used a convenience sample that is small and not representative for the world or even a small academic part of the world. However, if the databases and platforms provide replicable results, any set of researchers should get identical search results. Thus, we deem a convenience sample suitable, even though not perfect, for answering our research question.

Taken together, the replicability of search results seems to be at risk since they depend on several non-obvious factors. In order to address the challenge of low replicability and minimize its potential detrimental effects on research an update of guidelines for systematic reviews and meta-analyses like PRISMA-S is required. In our opinion, it would not be helpful, if researchers provide more details about how the search was conducted (e.g., from which university they accessed databases and platforms). Rather, researchers should publish the complete list of initial search hits. This list should be accompanied by filter variables which specify how initial search hits are excluded in the process of conducting a research synthesis. This update would make searching and selecting literature for systematic reviews and meta-analyses – from the initial search to the finally included studies - systematic and replicable.

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